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Review Article

A REVIEW ON KAWASAKI DISEASEN.Anitha*¹, Adeeba Husna¹, Syed Akbar²^{*1} Department of Pharmacology, Sultan-ul-Uloom College of Pharmacy, Road no.3, Banjara Hills, Hyderabad-500 034, Telangana, India.² Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Sultan-ul-Uloom College of pharmacy, Road no.3, Banjara Hills, Hyderabad-500 034, Telangana, India.**Abstract:**

Kawasaki disease is defined as an acute systemic vasculitis which majorly causes coronary artery abnormalities in 25% of untreated patients. Diagnosis is done basically in the light of clinical criteria; however, the presentation is roughly incomplete in approximately 25% of patients and this appears to subset at a nearly greater risk of serious complications. The main cause of Kawasaki disease is still unknown, however it is said that there is stimulation in the immune system after the infection in a genetically predisposed person. The infection caused is said to be highly suspected even though there is no specific bacteria or virus detected. Some of the infectious agents are Parvovirus, Staphylococcus aureus, Epstein-Bar virus, Chlamydia and Mycobacterium. This can be further confirmed by the occurrence of this disease in children. The occurrence of this disease is higher in children with affected parents than in all-purpose population. Inflammation of various organs like heart, meninges, lungs, lymph nodes, liver and strawberry tongue is seen during the acute phase. Different treatment methods used includes intravenous immunoglobulin, salicylates, beta blockers, statins and corticosteroids. The treatment is done with high doses of aspirin and immunoglobulin and the fever resolves within 4-5 days and there is a full recovery. Only few drugs are available for the treatment of this disease, and cardiac complications can be minimized only with beta-blockers and statins.

Key words: *Kawasaki disease, vasculitis, aneurysms, intravenous immunoglobulin and beta blockers.*

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INTRODUCTION:

Kawasaki disease (KD), also known as mucocutaneous lymph node syndrome which mainly affects the infants and children below 5 years. It is an acute systemic vasculitis which majorly causes coronary artery abnormalities in 25% of untreated patients [1]. It is known to surpass rheumatic heart disease as the leading cause of acquired cardiovascular disease in children in the developed world [2].

Tomisaku Kawasaki was the first to report kawasaki disease in the year 1967. The clinical signs and symptoms were described by him in 50 Japanese children with acute mucocutaneous lymph node syndrome [3]. After one year, Yamamoto T published the electro cardiogram abnormalities of KD patients [4]. In 1972, Japanese physicians finally established the relationship between KD and coronary vasculitis [5]. From that time KD has been described in many countries but mostly in Asia [6].

Diagnosis is done basically in the light of clinical criteria; however, the presentation is roughly incomplete in approximately 25% of patients, and this appears to subset at a nearly greater risk of serious complications [7]. Prevention of coronary artery dilation and aneurysms can be done by timely administration of intravenous immunoglobulin.

HISTORY

Tomisaku Kawasaki was the first to report this disease in a four-year-old child with a rash and fever at the Red Cross Hospital in Tokyo in January 1961 and he published a similar report on 50 other cases [8]. Later, Kawasaki and his colleagues were convinced of positive cardiovascular inclusion when they examined and announced 23 cases, of which 11 (48%) patients had variations from the normal recognized by an electrocardiogram [9]. Melish et al in the year 1976 described the same illness in 16 children in Hawaii [10]. Same diagnostic criteria was established independently for this disorder by Mellish and Kawasaki, which are still used today to make the diagnosis of Kawasaki disease [11].

A question was raised whether the disease just began amid the period in the vicinity of 1960 and 1970, however later a preserved heart of a seven-year-old kid who died in 1870 was analyzed and indicated three aneurysms of the coronary arteries with clots, and also pathologic changes consistent with Kawasaki disease [12].

EPIDEMIOLOGY

In the United States Rheumatology Clinic Population Study, Kawasaki disease appeared to represent 23% of all pediatric vasculitides and is the second most common multi-system vasculitis of infancy and childhood behind Henoch-Schonlein Purpura [13-15]. Although significant differences in epidemiological distribution have been seen worldwide [16], large number of factors appears to be relatively constant. These incorporate a male predominance, with a male-to-female apportion of in the vicinity of 1.5:1 and 2:1 [17-19]; marked seasonality, with increased occurrence in winter and early springs in temperate climates [20] and summer peaks in some Asian countries under 5 years of age [21]. An increased incidence in people of Asian descent, both inside and outside Asia was seen [22-24]. A rising frequency has been observed worldwide over time, may be due to increased incidence in people of Asian plunage, both observed worldwide over time, may be due to increased awareness and acknowledgement of the disease [25, 26].

ETIOLOGY

The main cause of KD is still unknown, however it is said that there is stimulation in the immune system after the infection in a genetically predisposed person [27]. The infection caused is said to be highly suspected even though there is no specific bacteria or virus detected [28], some of the infectious agents given are Parvovirus [29], Staphylococcus aureus [30], Epstein-Bar virus [31], Chlamydia & Mycobacterium [32]. This can be further confirmed by the occurrence of this disease in children. The prevalence of this disease is higher in children with affected parents than in all-purpose population [33]. But with still certain doubt that the mechanism of KD is triggered by immune system related symptoms [34, 35].

Clinical Manifestations

- It is usually accompanied with high fever lasting for more than 5 days
- Rash development takes place with peeling of skin between the chest and legs.
- Unusual swelling in hands and feet
- Redness in the eyes
- Glands gets enlarged especially in neck
- Inner mouth, tongue and throat gets irritated
- Joint pain with stomach ache, diarrhea and vomiting
- Swollen bright and strawberry tongue [36].

Figure no 1 and 2 shows the picture of straberry tongue and enlarged neck which is observed as

Fig no 1: Strawberry tongue

clinical symptoms in KD.

Fig no 2: Enlarged neck

KD has three stages:

1. Stage 1: Acute febrile phase
2. Stage 2: Sub acute phase
3. Stage 3: Convalescent phase

Stage 1 (0-10 days): The acute febrile phase is mainly characterized by fever. The fever in KD is usually higher than 39° C (102° F) and is unresponsive to antipyretics and antibiotic therapy [37]. Untreated children can have fever that lasts typically upto 1 to 2 weeks. Conjunctivitis (non purulent and bulbar), oropharyngeal changes (erythema, cracking of the lips, strawberry tongue, and non-exudative erythema of the oropharynx), polymorphous light eruption are the most common clinical features of KD in its acute phase [38]. Erythema or edema of the palms or soles occurs during the acute phase of KD. Cervical lymphadenopathy is not common in KD, found as a unilateral, firm and non-fluctuant node with a diameter greater than 1.5 cm [39].

Stage 2 (10-28 days): It begins with fever, rash and lymph adenopathy lasts up to one or two weeks after the beginning of the fever with persistent irritability. Anorexia, conjunctival infection, skin peeling of fingers, toes and thrombocytosis is seen which lasts for weeks. Risk of sudden death is high during this stage [40].

Stage 3: This stage begins after the disappearance of all clinical signs of illness usually 6 to 8 weeks after the onset of the illness and continues until the sedimentation rate is back to normal, at six to eight weeks after the onset of illness. Changes of the lips and oral cavity include erythema and cracking of the lips, strawberry tongue, and erythema of the oropharyngeal mucosa were seen. Adults and children have different intensity of symptoms. Adults' neck lymph nodes are affected more, 93% of adult's vs 15% of children, hepatitis 65% adult vs 10% in

children and arthralgia 61% adult vs 24–38% in children [41].

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY

Kawasaki disease involves systemic inflammation of medium sized blood vessels, mainly coronary arteries. Inflammation of various organs like heart, meninges, lungs, lymph nodes and liver is seen during the acute phase. Initially, polymorph nuclear invasion is found in vessel walls and mononuclear cells soon replace this [42]. Inflammation subsides during recovery but leaves behind fibrous connective tissue in the vessel wall along with proliferation of intima. This fibrin makes the vessels less elastic, stiffer and unable to generally stretch with higher arterial pressure but instead the arteries develop permanent bulging called aneurysms [43]. Aneurysms 8mm larger are at the most risk of rupturing, which reduces blood flow to the heart causing ischemia and potentially myocardial infarction. In some cases fibrosis doesn't lead to aneurysms but instead it makes the vessel walls thicker reducing the lumen diameter restricting blood flow which again leads to myocardial infarction or heart attack [44].

DIAGNOSIS

Kawasaki disease can be diagnosed only by clinical manifestation i.e, by managing medical signs and symptoms. No specific laboratory investigations are available for this condition. Establishment of diagnosis is difficult especially in the early course of the illness and mostly children are not diagnosed until they have visited to many health care providers.

The criteria for establishing the diagnosis classically include fever for 5 consecutive days and additionally four of the five diagnostic criteria which include the following [45].

1. Lips or oral cavity shows erythema or lips cracking is seen
2. A rash on the trunk can be seen
3. Hands or feet experiences swelling and erythema

4. Eyes are red (conjunctival infection)
5. At least 15 mm of swollen lymph node is seen at neck area
 - Blood tests
 - Complete blood count can diagnose normocytic anemia and later thrombocytosis.
 - Evaluation of the Erythrocyte sedimentation rate can be done.
 - C-reactive protein can be estimated.
 - Liver function tests may reveal evidence of hepatic inflammation and low serum albumin levels in this condition.
 - Other optional tests include:
 - Electrocardiogram may reveal evidence of ventricular dysfunction or, rarely, arrhythmia occurs due to myocarditis.
 - Subtle coronary artery changes or later true aneurysms can be established by Echocardiogram.
 - Hydrops (enlargement) of the gallbladder can be revealed by Ultrasound or computerized tomography scan.
 - White blood cells and protein in the urine (pyuria and proteinuria) without evidence of bacterial growth can be established by Urinalysis [46].

TREATMENT

- **IVIG (Intravenous immunoglobulin)**
For the treatment of Kawasaki disease the IVIG intravenous immunoglobulins are considered as standard treatment [47], provided in high doses which produces marked improvement usually observed within 24 hours. If the fever does not respond, further an additional dose may have to be given. In some of the rare cases, a third dose may be given to the child. IVIG is useful within the first seven days of onset of fever, in terms of preventing coronary artery aneurysm [48].
Mechanism of action: The efficacy of IVIG administered in the acute phase of KD is well established to reduce the prevalence of coronary artery abnormalities. Their exact mechanism of action is unknown [49]. They act by either suppressing the over active immune response or inhibiting the binding of WBC to damaging antibodies or removes all the antibodies from the body [50, 51].
Side effects: Headache, fever, fatigue, chills, flushing, urticaria, dizziness [52].
- **SALICYLATES (Aspirin)**
Salicylates therapy is an important part of the treatment. However salicylates are not more effective than IVIG. Aspirin therapy is provided in high doses until fever gets reduces, followed

by low dose until the patient went to home [53-56]. This is continued normally for two months which prevents the blood clotting. Aspirin therapy is not preferred for the children due to the association with the Reye's syndrome. The reason behind this is children with Kawasaki disease are given the aspirin for several months [57], these children should be regularly given vaccination for the varicella and influenza because these infections are likely to cause the Reye's syndrome. Sometimes the high doses of the aspirin cause the anemia [58].

Mechanism of action: They work by inhibiting the cyclooxygenase which reduces the chances of thrombus formation. They reduce the inflammation and inhibit the platelet aggregation thereby responsible for ischemia leading to MI.

Side effects: Upset of stomach, heartburn, dark urine, difficulty in hearing.

- **BETA BLOCKERS**

They act by reducing cardiac work and oxygen consumption as a consequence of decreased heart rate, ionotropic state and mean BP. Carvedilol, metoprolol succinate or bisoprolol are the β -blocking agents that have been shown to reduce the risk of death. The consideration of β -blocking agents has been incorporated into the long-term management algorithm for KD patients with large or giant aneurysms that persist.

Side effects: Dizziness, weakness, fatigue, headache, dry mouth, skin or eyes.

- **STATINS**

Mechanism of action: Hydroxy methyl glutaryl coenzyme-A reductase inhibitors (statins) are a cornerstone of therapy for the primary and secondary prevention of atherosclerotic cardiovascular events in adults. They inhibit the conversion of HMG CoA to mevalonate which decreases cholesterol production. In addition to lowering low-density lipoprotein cholesterol, statins have potentially beneficial pleiotropic effects on inflammation, endothelial function, oxidative stress, platelet aggregation, coagulation and fibrinolysis.

Side effects: Rhabdomyolysis, liver damage, increased blood sugar.

- **CORTICOSTEROIDS**

Corticosteroids are utilized when the other drugs for treatment does not works. However addition of corticosteroids to aspirin and globulin did not prove good outcome. Use of corticosteroid in the Kawasaki disease causes increased risk of coronary artery aneurysm, so its use is generally contraindicated.

CONCLUSION:

Kawasaki disease is a mucocutaneous lymph node syndrome in which blood vessels throughout the body become inflamed. The most common symptoms include a fever that lasts for more than five days, large lymph nodes in the neck, a rash in the genital area, redness of eyes, lips, palms or soles of the feet and strawberry tongue. The treatment is done with high doses of aspirin and intra venous immunoglobulin. Fever resolves within 4-5 days and there is a full recovery. The cardiac complications can be minimized with beta-blockers and statins.

Conflicts of Interests

The authors are not having any conflicts of interest.

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